

POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS OF APPLYING COACHING TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the application of coaching technology in the educational process and its significance in the formation of professional competencies. The research results show that innovative pedagogical technologies, in particular, the coaching approach, are an effective tool for increasing the activity of the student learning process, strengthening their motivation, developing logical thinking and leadership skills. However, the lack of time and the complexity of individual assessment are noted as the main disadvantages of this technology. The author, justifying the need to introduce elements of coaching in the higher education system, recommends a review of the professional competencies of teachers and mentors. It also emphasizes the effective application of coaching approaches in the student achievement assessment system.

Introduction

One of the conditions ensuring the competitiveness of a higher educational institution is the presence of an internal quality system that meets generally accepted requirements. Achieving high-quality professional training depends on the precise organization of the educational process, the correct choice of teaching methods, techniques, and technologies. According to S. Nikolaenko (2006), the implementation of a quality system ensures the competitiveness of a higher educational institution.

The use of innovative educational technologies ensures the training of highly qualified, professionally knowledgeable, logically thinking, motivated specialists capable of learning and self-development in their own and related fields. One of such technologies that ensure an effective educational process is coaching technology. Although the concept of coaching in education in Uzbekistan is not given as much attention as in many countries, we believe that it is necessary to effectively apply this technology in the national education system.

Discussion and results

Coaching, as a modern alternative pedagogical technology, is an effective means of forming students' competence in the educational process, the scientific foundations of which are set forth in the scientific research of scientists from the CIS and foreign countries.

The features of coaching technology, the prospects for introducing elements of this technology into the educational process of higher educational institutions are highlighted in the research of CIS (T. Borova, N. Goruk, S. Zhitskaya, O. Efimova, L. Kudryk, S. Romanova, G. Poberezskaya, Y. Surmak, O. Shevchuk) and foreign (D. Drukman, R. Bork, J. Whittmore, R. Dilts, B. Wutsek) scientists.

The features of coaching as a technology of professional training of specialists prompted us to conduct scientific research in this process.

In our opinion, the main advantages of using coaching as a pedagogical technology are:

- increasing the activity of the educational process;
- strengthening students' motivation to study the subject;
- identifying the abilities of students and demonstrating them as a person capable of creative thinking and logical analysis;
- development of students' leadership skills;
- ensuring high effectiveness of the educational process;
- formation of communicative skills;
- development of emotional intelligence.

Almost all researchers note the lack of time as a disadvantage of this technology'. We also note the impossibility of an individual approach to assessing learning outcomes, since the educational process is carried out in a group format. This leads to the replacement of outdated, traditional, and ineffective teaching methods and technologies with innovative, more pleasant methods. It should be especially noted that without the student's enthusiasm for learning, and the teacher's desire to carry out effective professional activity, the desire for self-improvement and development, it is impossible to achieve the final result - reflection. It should be noted that coaching is one of the ways to ensure that a person fully realizes their potential and achieves maximum effectiveness.

Based on the results of many theoretical studies and accumulated practical experience, we emphasize that the use of coaching technology in the organization of the educational process directs a person more to learning than to teaching. This is a successful combination not only of teaching methods, but also of management and interaction with people. The introduction of separate coach positions for students in the process of selecting and hiring scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher educational institutions is not provided for. Therefore, we recommend reviewing the content of the professional competencies of curator-teachers and coach-teachers, including tasks reflecting coaching approaches as consultants and coaches.

It is also advisable to update the content of official or functional duties of scientific and pedagogical workers related to the organization and implementation of practical laboratory classes and various types of practice. This is important from the point of view of creating conditions for the individual personal and professional development of future specialists.

Therefore, we confirm that the use of coaching technology in the educational process serves the development of the student's professional competencies in the field of specialization and the formation of their professional suitability.

Conclusion

Research on effective technologies for the professional training of future specialists is of great importance in the context of the formation of competitiveness in society. The process of training a specialist should not be limited to covering only existing and emerging opportunities and needs in the near future, but should also provide for the prospects of his professional development.

When assessing educational achievements, it is possible to take into account the possibilities of individual potential, through the active use of coaching as an educational technology. In this case, the activity of the teacher (coach) is aimed at searching for the most optimal ways to achieve the set goals and creating tasks for the prospects of personal and professional growth.

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